

D3.3: Communication Packages

Summary of Communication Activities M5 – M22

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 847066.

Smart Energy Services to Improve the Energy Efficiency of the European Building Stock

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Table of contents

1	Executive summary	6
2	Introduction	7
3	Communication and dissemination activities	8
3.1	Events & Webinars	8
3.2	Press releases	10
3.3	Articles (non-peer-reviewed)	11
3.4	Scientific papers (peer-reviewed)	13
3.5	Horizon 2020 project synergies	14
3.6	Newsletters and Community News	15
3.7	Videos	16
3.8	PowerPoint presentation template	17
3.9	Policy brief	17
4	Online presence	18
4.1	Website	18
4.2	LinkedIn	19
4.3	Twitter	19
4.4	YouTube	19
4.5	Enlit Europe	20
4.6	Open access to public deliverables	20
5	KPI Monitoring	21
5.1	KPI Overview	21
5.2	Targeted audience	25
6	Roadmap for M23-M36	27

7	Conclusions.....	29
8	Annex 1: SENSEI PowerPoint Presentation Template.....	30
9	Annex 2: Communication and dissemination activities monitoring file	34

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month (eg., M12 = month 12 of project period)
WP	Work Package

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1 Executive summary

This deliverable summarises the SENSEI project's communication and dissemination activities undertaken in the period M5-M22. It complements the first *Communication Packages* (D3.3) published in M4. The activities summarized here arise from the dissemination and communication strategy defined and described in the *Dissemination and Communication Plan* (D3.1).

The communication and dissemination efforts described in this deliverable cover activities such as participation in and presentations given at events; webinars and events organised in the scope of SENSEI; peer-reviewed scientific papers; non-peer-reviewed articles; press releases; collaboration with other H2020 projects; newsletters and communication materials sent to the SENSEI stakeholder community; video materials; PowerPoint presentation template and a policy brief.

Furthermore, the online presence of the project is addressed. The deliverable describes the development and the status of the SENSEI website, the social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube) and the SENSEI presence at the ENLIT Europe platform. It also accounts for the use of the Zenodo platform to ensure open access to all public deliverables.

The deliverable describes how the KPI's related to communication and dissemination activities are continuously monitored and gives an overview of the status as of M22. The overall picture is that SENSEI is very well on track with KPI's related to the online presence, the publication of articles and the presence at events. Where the KPI's are not yet reached, justification and mitigation actions are described. Finally, a roadmap for the dissemination and communication activities for the rest of the project period is provided which ensures that all KPI's are reached and, that the dissemination and exploitation of project results are successful.

2 Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a summary of the communication and dissemination activities undertaken in the period M5-M22, adding to the first *Communication Package* (D3.3) covering the period M1-M4. The activities undertaken in the previous period build upon the communication and dissemination strategy outlined in the *Dissemination and Communication Plan* (D3.1), slightly adapted in M12. This deliverable follows up on the strategy, the actions and the KPI's related to the communication and dissemination activities, and it provides a roadmap for the activities in the coming period to ensure that the project reaches all KPI's.

Following this introduction, section 2 provides an update on the communication and dissemination activities completed in the period M5-M22. Besides a brief description, it provides relevant numbers such as views, language, and media outlets.

Section 3 describes the development of the project's online presence. It reports on the numbers of website traffic, social media activities and additional online presence.

Section 4 presents an overview of the status of the different KPI's related to the communication and dissemination activities of the project. Where relevant, the KPI's are addressed with a brief explanation of the current status and planned mitigation actions.

Section 5 introduces a preliminary roadmap of the dissemination and communication activities planned for the duration of the rest of the project. This will ensure that all KPI's are reached and that the exploitation of project results is successful.

3 Communication and dissemination activities

The following section provides an update on the communication and dissemination work completed between M5 and M22. It includes a summary of both the activities conducted (e.g., workshops, conferences, papers, meetings) and the tools used to support the delivery of SENSEI messaging (e.g., newsletter, social media, videos). Most of the activities of this reporting period has been planned in the scope of the monthly Cluster 3 meetings as the place to discuss and plan activities under WP2 (stakeholder engagement) and WP3 (communication and dissemination) as these WP's are closely related. All consortium partners are present in these meetings that have proven an effective way to plan for relevant activities. Meeting minutes are stored in the project's shared Teams account.

3.1 Events & Webinars

As part of the project's dissemination efforts, SENSEI has participated in and given presentations at several events in the current reporting period. Table 1 below displays all events with either SENSEI presentations or events and webinars organised by SENSEI.

Event	Partner	Presentation title	Date	Attendees
India Smart Utility Week	GECO Global	Pay-for-performance to drive energy efficiency, poster session	03-03-2020	200 (estimated)
EUSEW	IEECP	New business models to de-risk investments and kick start the EU building renovation wave	18-06-2020	140
Sustainable Places	Omnia Energia, RAP, HEBES	The Boundary Cases for the P4P Rates	28-10-2020	7

Event	Partner	Presentation title	Date	Attendees
SuperScienceMe	UNICAL	Introducing SENSEI, poster session	27-11-2020	1000
EEFIG Working Group on Risk Assessment	IEECP	Oral presentation of SENSEI	07-12-2020	40
User-Centred Energy Systems Academy Webinar	RAP	Presentations of D4.4: Experience and lessons learned from pay-for-performance pilots for energy efficiency	15-12-2020	50
AIEE	UNICAL Omnia Energia, HEBES, IEECP, Factor4	SENSEI Special Session	17-12-2020	30
EU Green Week Partner Event	RAP, HEBES, Factor4	Advanced energy efficiency metering: the eensight method	25-05-2021	44
SENSEI Workshop, Italy	UNICAL, RAP, Sinergie	Energy efficiency as a resource for the electric system	26-05-2021	54
World Sustainable Energy Days	DBT, RAP, HEBES,	Innovation workshop: Innovative P4P business	25-06-2021	Not available yet

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Event	Partner	Presentation title	Date	Attendees
	IEECP, Factor4	model for building renovation		
World Sustainable Energy Days	RAP	Poster session	25-06-2021	Not available yet

Table 1: Summary of events with SENSEI participation/organised by SENSEI

3.2 Press releases

Halfway through the project, SENSEI launched a beta version of an advanced energy efficiency metering tool named *eensight*, developed in the scope of task 7, *Methods for the dynamic M&V of energy savings* (D7.1). Following that, the project prepared a press release informing about one of the key results at this stage. Table 2 below lists the entire number of media outlets the press release was sent to. **Green** indicates media outlets which published it. As can be seen, the press release had good coverage and succeeded in a 50% penetration of the media outlets it was sent to.

Media outlet	Language	Date
EndsEurope	English	19-04-2021
EnergyPress	English	19-04-2021
Flux50	English	19-04-2021
European Energy Innovation	English	19-04-2021
Recharge News	English	19-04-2021
Renovate Europe	English	19-04-2021
Rivista Energia	Italian	19-04-2021
Gestione Energia (FIRE)	Italian	19-04-2021
Wigwam News	Italian	19-04-2021

Media outlet	Language	Date
Money.it	Italian	19-04-2021
Rinnovabili.it	Italian	19-04-2021
La Voce	Italian	19-04-2021
ilQI	Italian	19-04-2021
QualEnergia.it	Italian	19-04-2021
BuildUp	English	19-04-2021
Energy Press	Greek	23-04-2021
Energia.gr	Greek	23-04-2021
Energia	English	23-04-2021
B2green.gr	Greek	23-04-2021
World Energy News	Greek	23-04-2021
Banking News	Greek	23-04-2021
Eco Press	Greek	07-05-2021
Eenergyin.gr	Greek	23-04-2021
Kataskevastirion.gr	Greek	23-04-2021
Palo.gr	Greek	24-04-2021
Facebook/ECO Press	Greek	08-05-2021
Facebook/Share from ECO Press	Greek	09-05-2021
Greek Energy Forum	Greek	10-05-2021

Table 2: Media coverage of press release

3.3 Articles (non-peer-reviewed)

The SENSEI project has written four non-peer-reviewed articles based on its findings to increase the outreach and impact of the ongoing work and the project's reputation. An overview is provided in Table 3 below.

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Title	Media Outlet & link	Date	Languages
European Sensei Report: Experience and Lessons Learned from P4P Pilots for Energy Efficiency in the EU	Recurve	18-06-2020	EN
7 H2020 projects partner up to advise EU leaders how to prepare buildings for the energy transition	Cordis	02-12-2020	EN
	BuildUp	01-12-2020	EN
	Construction21	03-12-2020	EN
Time for energy efficiency to be valued as a grid resource	ecee	18-12-2020	EN
	EnergyPost	27-01-2021	EN
	EU-China Energy Magazine	30-03-2021	Chinese
	AIEE Newsletter	27-01-2021	IT
Contribution to 'Towards a protocol for metered energy savings in UK buildings'	Green Finance Institute	01-02-2021	EN
Nieuwe tools om energierekeningen te verlagen (New tools to reduce energy bills)	Duurzaam Aktuel	06-07-2020	NL
Ξεκινά το έργο EE Horizon 2020 SENSEI για νέα μοντέλα υπηρεσιών ενεργειακής εξοικονόμησης (Launch of SENSEI)	EnergyPress Greece	27-12-2019	GR
El proyecto europeo SENSEI desarrolla modelos de pago por rendimiento para compensar la	ESEficiencia	09-06-2021	ES

Title	Media Outlet & link	Date	Languages
eficiencia energética como recurso energético (P4P to enable energy efficiency to be valued as a grid resource)			
Efficienza energetica: anche l'Unical nel progetto europeo "SENSEI" (Launch of SENSEI)	MeteoWeb	24-09-2019	IT
	Il Lametino	24-09-2019	IT

Table 3: Articles, non-peer-reviewed

3.4 Scientific papers (peer-reviewed)

To support the dissemination of project results two scientific papers based on the research done in the scope of SENSEI are published so far. The papers are listed in Table 4 below with data extracted on 28 June 2021.

Title	Outlet & Link	Date	Readers	Citations
<i>A review of deterministic and data-driven methods to quantify energy efficiency savings and to predict retrofitting scenarios in buildings</i>	Renewable & Sustainable Energy Reviews	Oct. 2020	107	6
<i>Devising Classes of Energy Efficiency Measure for Evaluating Pay-4-Performance Rate That Energy Provider Will Be Willing to Offer in Pay-4-Performance Scheme</i>	The 8th Annual International Sustainable Places Conference (SP2020)	Dec. 2020	167	0

Table 4: Peer-reviewed scientific papers

3.5 Horizon 2020 project synergies

SENSEI aims at creating connections with other initiatives and projects funded by the EU. A key element of the synergy networking strategy was to establish the group of Horizon 2020 sister projects. SENSEI contacted similar EU projects and executed a collaboration workshop to identify the common interests and aims of the group. Subsequently, the Horizon 2020 sister projects group has grown and currently consists of NOVICE, TripleA, LAUNCH, AmBIENce, RenOnBill, X-tendo, U-Cert, Quest, FrESCO, EN-TRACK and DEESME.

A big part of the collaboration between sister projects is to support each other in promoting and raising awareness of communication and dissemination activities to leverage all the projects' followers and stakeholder communities. In addition to engaging with sister projects' online communication activities (e.g., social media), joint activities such as the EUSEW side policy session (see Table 1: Summary of events with SENSEI participation/organised by SENSEI, p. 10) together with NOVICE, TripleA, LAUNCH, QualiTEE, Quest and UCERT projects are strengthening the collaboration and the dissemination and exploitation capability of all projects.

Under the leadership of SENSEI, the group of sister projects prepared and submitted a letter with policy recommendations for buildings in the energy transition to EU policymakers and stakeholders. IEECP received personalised confirmation that the letter was received by:

- the Cabinet of the Executive Vice-President Frans Timmermans
- Kurt Vandenberghe, Green Deal Adviser
- Sean Kelly, Member of the European Parliament

In addition to this, SENSEI published the letter at Cordis, Build UP and Construction 21 (please see section 3.3 for details). All projects promoted it in their newsletters with an outreach of 1600 subscribers in total. It was heavily shared on Twitter and LinkedIn. The letter is available at [Zenodo](#) and has 292 unique views and 148 unique downloads (pr. 28 June 2021).

Lastly, the SENSEI partner ADV has been appointed to the advisory board of the Smartbuilt4EU project and is involved in the task force related to financing and business models, allowing for synergies (i.e., with Task 6.3) and promotion of project results.

The latest update in collaborations is the developing collaboration between SENSEI and the Horizon 2020 project [FrESCO](#) for the organisation of a joint event at the Sustainable Places 2021 conference.

3.6 Newsletters and Community News

SENSEI will publish six newsletters in total during the project period. As per M22, three newsletters have been published, on average once every six months. Newsletters are sent to subscribers to the online stakeholder community (set up via Mailchimp) and shared via the website and social media channels.

In addition to this, subscribers are regularly contacted with relevant information material such as invitations for events or project surveys. Table 5 gives an overview of the communication and dissemination material sent via Mailchimp (data updated 28 June 21).

Title	Date	Recipients	Opens	Clicks
Newsletter No. 1	05-05-2020	29	16	9
Newsletter No. 2	18-11-2020	91	25	11
Newsletter No. 3	20-05-2021	118	43	12
Other communication materials sent to the online stakeholder community				
Community News 01	25-06-2020	56	23	7
Community News 02	03-09-2020	79	30	5
Presentation of sister projects	21-10-2020	91	31	3
How to prepare buildings for the energy transition (letter to policymakers)	01-12-2020	91	23	5
T8.1 Stakeholder Survey	05-05-2021	120	41	11
Reminder of T8.1 Stakeholder Survey	01-06-2021	125	40	6

Title	Date	Recipients	Opens	Clicks
Invitation to SENSEI at World Sustainable Energy Days	10-06-2021	128	39	9

Table 5: Communication material sent via Mailchimp

3.7 Videos

In the period M4-M22 eight videos have been uploaded to the SENSEI YouTube channel including the first of two project videos, describing in one minute the core of the project in a visual and easily understandable manner. The project video is embedded on the front page of the website and uploaded to the YouTube channel. In addition, a ten-minute video introduction of the findings of *Experiences and lessons learned from P4P pilots* (D4.4) is embedded on the website and uploaded on the YouTube channel together with the video recordings from several presentations at events and webinars. Please see the complete list in Table 6 (data from 28 June 2021). The table is colour coded with **green** indicating videos uploaded to the project's YouTube channel and **blue** for videos uploaded to channels of other organisations. This table does *not* reflect the numbers of views at the project's website.

Title	Description	Date	Views
What is SENSEI?	Project introduction video	04-05-2020	427
SENSEI, PAY-FOR-PERFORMANCE to drive energy efficiency in Europe	IEECP Lunch seminar	27-05-2021	58
New business models to de-risk investments and kick start the EU building renovation wave	EUSEW Webinar recordings.	30-05-2020	256
Experience and lessons learnt from P4P pilots	Video presentation of D4.4 findings.	04-09-2020	85

Title	Description	Date	Views
Business & Energy Efficiency Models	Paper session at Sustainable Places 2020 (2 presentations)	11-11-2020	34
SENSEI Special Session	AIEE Symposium Recordings	11-01-2021	39
Advanced Energy Efficiency Metering - the eensight method	Webinar recordings from EU Green Week partner event.	26-05-2021	56
Enabling Energy Efficiency as a Grid Resource	Recordings of SENSEI stakeholder workshop in Italy.	27-05-2021	54

Table 6: SENSEI video material

3.8 PowerPoint presentation template

To ensure a unified visual identity, a PowerPoint presentation template to be used by partners when presenting SENSEI at events and webinars has been designed (see Annex 1: SENSEI PowerPoint Presentation Template). The template gives a presentation of the stakeholder community, the social media channels, and the sister projects. The presentation of SENSEI differs according to the targeted audience.

3.9 Policy brief

As part of Communication Package 2 under Task 3 (WP3), a policy brief was produced and promoted to support the development of EU policies related to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. The policy brief was uploaded to [Zenodo](#), to allow direct access from the SENSEI website. To target the outreach of the policy brief, it was sent directly to 41 EU policymakers by email and, to the Chair of the Working Group on Regulation from the [BRIDGE](#) initiative representing 56 Horizon 2020 projects working with EU policies, inviting him to share with and ask for comments from all members of the working group. In addition, it has been promoted on the SENSEI website and the project's social media channels (data for outreach not yet available).

4 Online presence

In the *Dissemination and Communication Plan* (D3.1), the social media strategy defined LinkedIn and Twitter as the key social media channels of the project and YouTube as the platform used to upload video materials. The project website is the main hub of the project with all project findings and news available. In this chapter, the development of the period M5-M22 will be summarized.

Before moving on to the summary of the social media activities, it is worth mentioning that the continuously ongoing KPI monitoring (see section 5: KPI Monitoring) has led to the introduction of a 'social media alert', also described in the adaption of the *Dissemination and Communication Plan* (D3.1) in M13. The social media alert is an email sent to all SENSEI partners every time a new post is published. The email contains direct links to the post(s). The aim is to take advantage of the professional network of all partners by making it as easy as possible for them to contribute to the project's online outreach.

4.1 Website

In addition to the renovation of the website described in the *Dissemination and Communication Plan* (D3.1), the website has been updated with [a list of upcoming deliverables](#). The website is regularly updated with news, events and information on the project's deliverables and results. Also, project newsletters and other communication materials can be found here. To ensure a dynamic and relevant website, the Twitter feed is embedded on the front page. Furthermore, the project video and the video presentation of *Experiences and Lessons Learned from P4P Pilots* (D4.4) have been embedded as mentioned under section 3.7.

To monitor the website traffic and to be able to report on the KPI related to the use of the project website Google Analytics has been installed. As seen in Figure 1: Extract from Google Analytics, the number of visitors in the period M4-M22 amounts to 3650 new users (data extracted on 15 June 2021). As the goal by the end of the project is 1500 visitors the KPI has been reached by now.

Furthermore, the graph below shows several peaks in the number of page visitors. These peaks are related to the launch of the project newsletters (May 2020, March 2021) and other promoted communication materials such as the letter to policymakers created with

the sister projects (described in section 3.5 Horizon 2020 project synergies), presentations at events (AIEE in December 2020) and not least the press release on *ensight* in April 2021 as well as the following webinars.

Figure 1: Extract from Google Analytics

4.2 LinkedIn

The SENSEI LinkedIn profile has gained 305 followers (data extracted on 15 June 2021), exceeding the KPI of 250 established in the GA. The project has posted 50 updates so far which amounts to an average of 2.3 posts per month, also exceeding the KPI of 30 posts by the end of the project.

4.3 Twitter

SENSEI's Twitter profile has gained 374 followers (data extracted 28 June 2021), exceeding the KPI set to 250 followers. The KPI for the number of tweets by the end of the project was set to 30 and has now been reached with a total of 178 tweets.

4.4 YouTube

SENSEI set up a YouTube channel to upload and share the video materials produced for the project. The project has uploaded four videos with a total amount of 622 views as per 28 June 2021. The KPI is 1000 views (see also section 5:

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KPI Monitoring).

4.5 Enlit Europe

As of M20, SENSEI is featured in the Enlit Europe platform and is now present in the [EU projects zone](#), thus gaining visibility in the Enlit EU Projects Marketplace and gaining to participate in networking opportunities with relevant stakeholders, with whom the project consortium aims to hold conversations and interactions that support P4P schemes in the context of the energy transition.

4.6 Open access to public deliverables

As a Horizon 2020 research and innovation project, SENSEI must enable open access to public deliverables. Therefore, all public deliverables (and other communication materials) are uploaded to the [SENSEI community](#) set up on the Zenodo platform. For the numbers of views and downloads of the uploaded material, please see section 5. In addition, all public deliverables are promoted on the project's social media channels and the SENSEI website.

5 KPI Monitoring

The purpose of continuously monitoring the communication and dissemination related KPI's is to be able to detect challenges and enable mitigation actions in due time. This chapter provides an overview of the status of the KPI's and addresses the key points of attention. The overall impression of the KPI's displayed in Table 7, is that SENSEI is very well on track with its communication and dissemination activities. However, there is a few points of attention that is necessary to address as the project progress. They will be commented on in section 5.1. Section 5.2 provides a summary of the audience targeted with the dissemination and communication activities.

5.1 KPI Overview

The sources for monitoring the KPI's varies according to the communication material.

- Mailchimp serves as the software for sending communication materials to the stakeholder community and is used to monitor the receivers and opens of project newsletters.
- Google Analytics is installed on the project website and provide data for KPI monitoring related to the website.
- The social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube) offer analytical tools to monitor followers and the number of posts.
- Zenodo is used to allow open access to public deliverables and monitors the number of views, downloads and cross-citations.
- The SENSEI monitoring file is a shared spreadsheet located in the project's Teams account, accessible for all consortium partners. All communication and dissemination efforts such as articles, social media posts, press releases, videos etc., are reported in this document, registering the media outlet, the partner, the date and language, the targeted audience, the number of audiences reached and, a link. If a link is not available, proof of the communication activity is uploaded to the project's Teams account as well. A screenshot of the monitoring file is available in

Annex 2: Communication and dissemination activities monitoring file.

Table 7 below provides an overview of all KPI's and communication and dissemination goals. The table is based on data extracted 28 June 2021 and colour coded as follows:

Green indicates already reached KPI's.

Yellow indicates KPI's well on track.

Orange indicates special points of attention, commented on below the table.

Grey indicates KPI's not relevant yet.

Activities	KPI	M1 -M22	Goal at the end of the project
Project website	N° of visitors (accumulated)	3901	500
Publications	N° of visitors (accumulated)	2297	250
	N° of downloads (accumulated)	1963	500
Newsletter	N° of opens of each Newsletter (accumulated)	83	250
Events	N° of events featuring SENSEI	13	25
	N° of participation in webinars and stakeholder workshops* (accumulated)	98	100
	N° of participation in trainings / capacity building events (accumulated)	Not relevant yet	50
Press release	N° of distinctive outlets (coverage)	2	4
Scientific papers	N° of citations from publications and scientific papers (cross-citation)	2	50

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Activities	KPI	M1 -M22	Goal at the end of the project
Supportive guidelines	Use of EngageSuite content (N° of users)	Not relevant yet	50
Twitter	N° of posts	178	30
	N° of followers	374	250
LinkedIn	N° of posts	57	30
	N° of followers	305	250
YouTube	N° of views	622	1000
Media cases in national languages/per consortium country in average	Italy	3	5
	Denmark	0	5
	Spain	2	5
	The Netherlands	1	5
	Greece	14**	5
	Germany	0	5
	Belgium	0	
Articles targeting the general public	N° of articles	7	4

Table 7: KPI overview

* Data from WSED participants are not yet available.

**Includes the publication of the press release in M20 in 12 different media outlets.

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Number of opens of each newsletter

The KPI decided in the GA was to publish six newsletters with an accumulated opening rate of 250 by the end of the project. Currently, the SENSEI project has published three newsletters with a total of 83 opens with an average opening rate of 40,7%. With only three newsletters to go, it is difficult to reach the KPI of 250 opens. However, the online community has been targeted with additional material. In total, eleven emails have been sent, including community news, a summary of the policy recommendations developed with the SENSEI sister project, information on a survey under T8.1 and, an invitation for the stakeholders to join World Sustainable Energy Days. Thus, the total number of opens amounts to 339, an average opening rate of 32,7%. When comparing to the [general statistics of the opening rates on Mailchimp](#) (the software used for SENSEI's community communication) which is only at 21,33%, the numbers indicate a very high interest from the audience..

Number of events featuring SENSEI

In the GA, SENSEI committed to 'featuring' SENSEI at 25 events. At this point, we have registered SENSEI presence at 11 events (see Table 1, p. 10), ranging from local events in partner countries like the workshop organised in Italy to international events like the World Sustainable Energy Days. With the Covid-19 pandemic situation still causing a lot of restrictions and cancellation or postponement of events, it has proven difficult to be as active in disseminating project results at events as originally planned. However, with several key deliverables to be published in the coming months; the pandemic restrictions being increasingly suspended and, an increased focus on being present at events it is reasonable to assume that SENSEI will reach the KPI of being featured at 25 events.

Number of citations from publications and scientific papers (cross-citation)

With two peer-reviewed scientific papers published so far and six registered cross-citations it seems difficult to reach the KPI of 50 cross-citations, at the end of the project. Although the project deliverables published at Zenodo have had a high number of readers and downloads (2297 unique views and 1963 unique downloads registered) there are no registered cross-citations. Currently, SENSEI partners are working on three scientific articles to be published in peer-reviewed journals (see section 0: Roadmap for M23-M36) which will help to increase the number of cross-citations.

YouTube: Number of views

By the end of the project, SENSEI is to have 1000 views on the project's YouTube channel. Currently, there is a total of 622 views or 59,4%. With one more professionally produced project video coming up and the recordings of upcoming events, webinars, and workshops, it seems very likely that SENSEI will also reach this KPI.

Media cases in the national languages of the consortium countries

As per the GA, SENSEI has committed to media coverage of 5 media cases in local/national media in each of the consortium countries *on average*. For some countries, it has proven hard to publish in the local press as Table 7 reveals. In addition, the language used for discussing energy efficiency within the industry is English in countries such as Belgium and Denmark. However, as the table reports a total of 22 media cases, amounting to more than three media cases per consortium country, it is reasonable to say that also this KPI will be reached.

5.2 Targeted audience

To ensure that all stakeholder categories are targeted with the SENSEI communication and dissemination materials, the monitoring of the activities includes the registration of which stakeholder group is targeted with the different communication efforts. The numbers in Table 8 below are based on the data registered in the monitoring file. As can be seen, the communication and dissemination efforts of the project cover all stakeholder categories well.

Stakeholder category	No. of targeted communication items
Scientific community	108
Industry	117
Civil society	102
General public	136
Policymakers	118

Stakeholder category	No. of targeted communication items
National level authorities	107
Regional actors	104
Local actors	122
Media	100
Energy agencies	105
Others	75

Table 8: Overview of targeted audience

6 Roadmap for M23-M36

At the second project meeting held in March 2021, the KPI's were evaluated in plenum by the consortium partners. Following this evaluation, the dissemination and communication activities for the rest of the project period were planned.

Firstly, at the project meeting, a brainstorming session was executed to gather ideas and topics for future articles (scientific and non-scientific targeting the public), events and press releases. The outcome of this session serves as a bank of ideas to generate sufficient communication materials of the highest quality.

Secondly, after the project meeting, an initial roadmap for the rest of the project period was created to ensure that (i) the project will reach all KPI's and (ii) the exploitation of project results is supported by engaging and qualified communication and dissemination activities.

The roadmap for the period M23-M36 is displayed in Table 9 below. It is important to stress that this roadmap is meant as flexible guidelines, as such it does not show the full picture of upcoming activities. To ensure relevant communication activities in the rest of the project period this roadmap will be altered continuously. In addition to the public deliverables which will be followed by online promotion activities, the roadmap shows planned events, articles, press releases and videos. This will be supplemented by the monthly updates on the project's social media profiles which are not displayed.

M23	
M24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific article: "Pioneering a performance-based future for energy efficiency: Lessons learned from a comparative review analysis of Pay-for-Performance programmes" (working title). Scientific Journal: Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews/August 2021 (work in progress)
M25	
M26	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event: Sustainable Places: Several applications are currently under preparation, one of these being a joint workshop with the Horizon 2020 project FrESCO
M27	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D6.3, D7.3 • Article, general public: Public Administration Role as P4P Owner vs traditional Grants • Event: Presentation at ECOMONDO
M28	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D6.4, D6.5 • Press release: TBD • Article, general public: Public challenge on the business plan: outline the benefits of an EE aggregator, and experience from other aggregators, in a EU-wide outlet.
M29	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event: AIEE • Event: SuperScienceMe • Scientific paper: "Strategy recommendations for the development of Pay-for-Performance schemes in the EU: An integrated SWOT-AHP analysis" (working title). Scientific Journal: Energy Policy Submission date: December 2021 (work in progress).
M30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event, World Sustainable Energy Days: SENSEI will be present at WSED '22 with a workshop. • D5.4, D7.4, D8.3 • Scientific paper: A scientific paper based on the findings of D7.1 is planned. Working title and journal of publication to be decided.
M31	
M32	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Article, general public: Synergies between energy efficiency retrofitting projects and tenants health: (Led by RAP Local/international)
M33	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event: EU Green Week
M34	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event: eceee Summer Study. SENSEI is planning an important stakeholder capacity building workshop at the eceee summer study conference with the collaboration of the Swiss utility provider SIG
M35	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Second project video: Summing up the improved understanding of P4P schemes in an EU context.
M36	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D7.2 • Press release on final project results • Article targeting general public on final project results

Table 9: Roadmap for communication and dissemination activities

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7 Conclusions

In the period M5-M22 of the project, the dissemination and communication efforts have successfully facilitated internal and external interactions that helped create awareness around the project. Furthermore, the monthly Cluster 3 meetings have proven effective to create relevant content on a continuous basis and to engage most partners in the communication and dissemination efforts. An evaluation of the KPI targets showed that SENSEI is very well on track with almost all KPI's. Where it is not the case, necessary mitigation actions have been planned and a roadmap for coming dissemination and communication activities has been created to ensure that all KPI's will be reached and to support the exploitation potential of the project; the primary focus of the third year.

8 Annex 1: SENSEI PowerPoint Presentation Template

EVENT NAME Location and date
 <i>Smart Energy Services to Improve the Energy Efficiency of the European Building Stock</i>
Presentation title Partner / Speakers name
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What is SENSEI?

Problem Rebates and incentives for Energy Efficiency Programs are paid up front
→ EE Programs need to rely on deemed energy savings

Solution Enable Energy Efficiency as a resource
Attract private financing by turning an EE Programs value into investable asset

Pay-for-Performance (P4P) schemes as a business model
SENSEI will develop P4P schemes which are applicable in an EU context.

SENSEI Consortium consists of 13 parties and is funded by the EU Horizon2020 programme.

Stakeholder Community – Why Join?

Influence

- ✦ Influence the development by participating in surveys, webinars, workshops
- ✦ Identify potential pilots for P4P

Knowledge

- ✦ Access to interactive e-learning system, translating into early mover advantage
- ✦ Receive biannual newsletter, community news and publications

Visibility

- ✦ Have your company logo flagged alongside SENSEI activities all over Europe (optional)
- ✦ Showcase your expertise, experience and discuss SENSEI's latest progress during our events

Activities

- ✦ Provide feedback and challenge our findings according to your availability and interest
- ✦ Attend our workshops, webinars and other activities with your peers

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Stakeholder community – How to Join

To join the SENSEI Stakeholder community, go to our website at www.senseih2020.eu and click the button in the top right corner

Horizon2020 Sister Projects

At the SENSEI website you can also learn more about our sister projects.

These projects are investigating ways to enable the mass adoption of energy efficiency measures from different perspectives.

Go to the SENSEI website and learn more.

Let's join forces!

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sensei

Any questions or comments

Thank you!

Sign up to receive our Newsletter at www.senseih2020.eu

Sign up to join our Stakeholder Community:
<https://senseih2020.eu/stakeholders/>

Frontpage :

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9 Annex 2: Communication and dissemination activities monitoring file

This is a screenshot of a part of the monitoring file. It does not encompass the total amount of data in the spreadsheet.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V
	Partner	Activity	Event	Country	Language	Date	Description	Scientific Community	Industry	NGOs	General Public	Policy makers	National level authorities	Regional actors	Local actors	Media	Energy agencies	Others	Outreach (total n° of reached people, even if estimation)	Proof (Y/N) - please if Yes, upload in SENSEI dropbox (WP3>Dissemination)	Link if any	Additional comments
1																						
2	[CIMNE]	Article (general public)	ESEFICIENCIA (Grupo TecmaR	Spain	Spanish	09-06-2021	Report about EEnsign and SENSEI	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		unknown		EU project	
171	[SINERGIE]	Social media post	Sustainable Places	Online	Italian	27-10-2020	Tweet				X				X					Y	https://twitter.com/Sinergie_NET/status/1344444444	
172	[SINERGIE]	Social media post	Sharing SENSEI 2° newsletter	Online	Italian	20-11-2020	Linkedin post				X				X					Y	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6888888888888888888	
173	[SINERGIE]	Social media post	Sharing SENSEI 2° newsletter	Online	Italian	20-11-2020	Facebook post				X				X							
174	[SINERGIE]	Social media post	Sharing SENSEI 2° newsletter	Online	Italian	20-11-2020	Tweet				X				X					Y	https://twitter.com/Sinergie_NET/status/1344444444	
175	[SINERGIE]	Social media post	Policy recommendations to pr	Online	Italian	02-12-2020	Tweet				X											
176	[SINERGIE]	Social media post	Policy recommendations to pr	Online	Italian	02-12-2020	Linkedin post				X				X							
177	[SINERGIE]	Social media post	Policy recommendations to pr	Online	Italian	02-12-2020	Facebook post				X				X							
178	[SINERGIE]	Social media post	Promo of WSED2021 Stakehol	Online	Italian	04-12-2020	Tweet				X				X							
179	[SINERGIE]	Social media post	Promo of WSED2021 Stakehol	Online	Italian	04-12-2020	Linkedin post				X				X							
180	[SINERGIE]	Social media post	Promo of WSED2021 Stakehol	Online	Italian	04-12-2020	Facebook post				X				X							
181	[SINERGIE]	Social media post	Participation in AIEE Energy S	Online	Italian	09-12-2020	Tweet				X				X							
182	[SINERGIE]	Social media post	Participation in AIEE Energy S	Online	Italian	09-12-2020	Linkedin post				X				X							
183	[SINERGIE]	Social media post	Participation in AIEE Energy S	Online	Italian	09-12-2020	Facebook post				X				X							
184	[SINERGIE]	Social media post	KICK OFF MEETING		Italian	17-09-2019	Communication of SINERGIE's participation				X								2812	Y	https://www.dropbox.com/s/1234567890/1234567890.pdf?dl=1	2 Facebook - 1 LinkedIn
185	[UNICAL]	Article (general public)	Launch of SENSEI	Italy	Italian	19-09-2019	Launching of sensei	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x				http://www.meteoweb.eu/2019/09/efficien
186	[UNICAL]	Article (general public)	Launch of SENSEI	Italy	Italian	24-09-2019	Launching of sensei	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x				http://www.lametino.it/Ultimora/efficienza
187	[UNICAL]	Event exhibition or post	Promo of SENSEI	Online	Italian	27/11/2020	Introducing SENSEI project	X		X				X	X	X			1000			https://www.superscienceme.it/il-progetto
188	[UNICAL]	Event organisation (workshop)	SENSEI Special session at AIEE	Online	English	17-12-2020	Special session in Symposium	X	X	X	X	X								30		https://zoom.us/rec/share/s5nM10hH2EG
189	[UNICAL]	Social media post	Advise to EU Leader by 7 H20	Online	English	03-12-2020	linkedin	X	X		X									200		https://www.linkedin.com/posts/nicola-sor
190	[UNICAL]	Social media post	Announcing SENSEI special se	Online	English	10-12-2020	Linkedin	X	X	X	X	X								130		https://www.linkedin.com/posts/nicola-sor
191	[UNICAL]	Social media post	Promo of SENSEI 2nd newslett	Online	English	11-12-2020	Linkedin	X	X	X	X	X								50		https://www.linkedin.com/posts/nicola-sor
192	[UNICAL]	Social media post	Promo of deliverable 4.2	Online	English	17-12-2020	Linkedin	X	X	X	X	X								35		https://www.linkedin.com/posts/nicola-sor
193	[UNICAL]	Social media post	Promo of paper 'Time for ener	Online	English	20-12-2020	Linkedin	X	X	X	X	X								40		https://www.linkedin.com/posts/nicola-sor

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Communication Packages

- Summary of Communication Activities
up to M5

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Smart Energy Services to Improve the Energy Efficiency of the European Building Stock

Deliverable n°:	D3.3
Deliverable name:	Communication Packages – Summary of Communication Activities
Version:	1.0
Release date:	01/01/2020
Dissemination level:	Public
Status:	Draft
Author:	GECO – Carsten Gydahl-Jensen

This report contains a summary of communication activities in the first four (4) months of project SENSEI. It is the first of three reports during the lifetime of the project. Next reports will be in month 22 and 35 of the project.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 847066.

Document history:

Version	Date of issue	Content and changes	Edited by
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3	28/12/2019	Final version	Carsten Gydahl GECO

Peer reviewed by:

Partner	Reviewer
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Table of Contents

Executive summary		6
1 Introduction		7
1.1	Scope of the Deliverable	7
1.2	Structure of the Document	7
2 Communication Activities		8
2.1	Preparations	8
2.1.1	Initial preparation steps towards project Kick-off meeting	8
2.1.2	Initial establishment of communication channels	9
2.1.3	Project profile, presentation and communication design templates	9
2.2	Carried out	11
2.2.1	Project website and online presence	11
2.2.2	Project flyer, infographics and poster	14
2.2.3	Identification of key messages and selling points	17
2.2.4	Press release and initial invitation to stakeholders	19
2.2.5	Partners online presentation of the project and e-news	20
2.2.6	Presentation of the project at events	21
2.3	Scheduled	22
2.3.1	Initial description and first version of presentation video	22
2.3.2	Dissemination and Communication Plan	24
2.3.3	Collaboration with other EU projects	25

2.3.4 Scientific publications and dissemination of knowledge

26

3	Lessons learned and adjustments	26
4	Conclusion.....	27
5	Appendix.....	27

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
GA	Grant Agreement
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
P4P	Pay-for-Performance
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

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Executive summary

SENSEI is a project based on thorough research in energy efficiency. SENSEI will put research into action and will in this process involve market players in this process. Communication activities towards market players in the energy and financial sector is crucial to achieve a go-to-market success. Therefore, it is highly important to engage in effective communication activities towards potential stakeholders to increase engagement in the co-creation process of P4P in the European energy market.

Up to month four in the project SENSEI much effort has been put into establishing the fundamentals in communication and dissemination such as project presentation, flyer, infographics. Still some fine-tuning needs to be done and further actions have to be taken to bring the essentials up front for communication purposes.

The project consortium has during the first months of the project lifetime identified a challenge in the flow of knowledge and content internally. This challenge is still discussed, and the solution is to establish an Editorial Board. The Editorial Board was proposed to bring the partner's expert closer to the communication table to mitigate misconceptions and unfortunate interpret of P4P in the external communication of P4P. Further steps will soon be taken in the consortium as soon as the purpose of the Editorial Board is clear.

10 Introduction

10.1 Scope of the Deliverable

The present deliverable, Summary of Communication Activities, is developed to sum up on ongoing activities regarding reaching out to potential collaborators. This includes other EU projects and companies that have important information and knowledge for project SENSEI to incorporate. Initially, the purpose of Summary of Communication Activities is to pave the road for further communication activities and point out essential communication needs to reach the project goal.

GECO Global is the leader of the production of D3.3 and will lead the ongoing communication activities during the project lifetime. During Kick-off Meeting (KoM), a cluster of partners in communication, dissemination and outreach was established (Cluster 3). The task “Communication and dissemination” is a dynamic process, and this document is for reporting on the progressions in this process.

Description of task 3.3 in the Grant Agreement:

The project will produce three communication packages, which aim at broad communication of the intentions and results of the project:

1. Presentation on the project, aims and objectives, methods, consortium, etc. at the beginning of the project. This will include the production of a flyer, poster, press release, a short presentation video (scribing technique), and communication design templates. The video will be published on the project’s website, on YouTube and other video sharing systems.
2. Communication of results halfway through the project. This will include a policy brief, press release on main results, and a presentation to be used by the partners for presenting the SENSEI results at meetings, conferences, etc.
3. Communication of results at the end of the project. This will include a policy brief, and a summary presentation to recap the key findings and results tailored for the project partners’ own use enabling them to exploit the project work post-SENSEI. The final communication package will also include a video (scribing techniques), which documents the results of the project. It will be published on the project’s website, on YouTube and other video sharing systems.

Led by GECO with the support of RAP and DBT, and FACTOR4 (to help craft the content from the ESCOs’ perspective), OMNIA ENERGIA (to help craft the content from the energy providers’ perspective) and GENCAT (to help craft the content from the building owners’ perspective).

1.2 Structure of the Document

The present document reports on communication activities in project SENSEI which is bullet 1:

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Presentation on the project, aims and objectives, methods, consortium, etc. at the beginning of the project. This will include the production of a flyer, poster, press release, a short presentation video (scribing technique), and communication design templates. The video will be published on the project's website, on YouTube and other video sharing systems.

In order to deliver a proper description of this document, it will include the following:

1. Initial preparation steps towards project KoM.
2. Initial establishment of communication channels.
3. Project profile, presentation and communication design templates.
4. Project website and online presence
5. Project flyer, infographics and poster
6. Identification of key messages and selling points
7. Press release and initial invitation to stakeholders
8. Partners online presentation of the project and e-news
9. Initial description and first version of the presentation video
10. Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP)
11. Collaboration with other EU projects
12. Scientific publications and dissemination of knowledge

The report contains a summary of communication activities in the first four (4) months of project SENSEI. It is the first of three reports during the lifetime of the project. Next reports will be in month 22 and 35 of the project.

11 Communication Activities

11.1 Preparations

11.1.1 Initial preparation steps towards project Kick-off meeting

In preparation for the KoM, a corporate communication profile was drafted. The WPL of Communication and Dissemination did some initial preparations to ensure that all partners got aligned in what was expected from them in project dissemination and communication activities. By providing a corporate project profile and presenting according to the guidelines, it was possible to stress the importance of the communication and branding of the project.

The WP leader prepared prior to the KoM:

1. Initial establishment of communication channels.
2. Project profile, presentation and communication design templates.

11.1.2 Initial establishment of communication channels

The social media channels like LinkedIn.com, Twitter.com and Youtube.com were established. SENSEI is present on selected social media networks. These are crucial for the overall communication and dissemination activities and will be visible on relevant pages of the website. Bridging the gap between the SENSEI website and social media profiles, will be essential to spread messages through the right digital channels to the right target group at the right time.

Figure 1: Three (3) social media channels in project SENSEI

Initially, social media channels were used to communicate the settlement of the consortium and the initial organizing of WPs and tasks at the KoM. In addition, the consortium will use social media to ensure that information is shared with relevant audiences timely. Partners will extend the knowledge of SENSEI, distribute results on the go, and help create attention for the project's events on social media. Regular tweets from the project twitter account (@sensei_h2020) will also work in collaboration with the project website, and stakeholders will be motivated to make use of Twitter.

11.1.3 Project profile, presentation and communication design templates

Prior to the KoM, the WPL started the production of a corporate project identity and introduced a draft logo and design templates that included presentation templates. Introducing a corporate identity is to ensure a common communication profile and from the beginning stress the importance of the communication from KoM to the end of the project.

The SENSEI logo is built up of a simple font set combined with a recognisable green clover. Each leaf carries a SENSEI message:

Stakeholder impact:

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Figure 2: Initial SENSEI logo

During the KoM, the intention was to get feedback from partners on the communication profile. After the KoM adjustments were made, and the WPL made some alternative logos and send out a poll to the consortium for the partners to vote for their favourite logo.

Figure 3: Original logo and four (4) alternative logos for the poll.

After the logo poll, the final logo became the clover logo. The colours in the logo and a colour palette is a part of the communication profile.

Green, the color of life, is chosen as the main color, because it is associated with renewal, nature, and energy, as well as meanings of growth, harmony, freshness, and environment. Green is also traditionally associated with money, finances, banking, and ambition.

The light purple is the secondary color to the primary color green. Purple combines the calm stability of blue and the fierce energy of red. Purple is used in the font of the logo. Purple will also be used for icons and social media graphics.

Anthracite is a chalky and earthy near-black or very dark grey. The color anthracite will be used mostly for content, outline and text.

Orange is an energizing, positive color. The light creamy orange will mostly be used as an alternative gradient color and light background for text or pictures.

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The red brown is chosen as a contrast color to go with the light orange and will be used for links and buttons e.g. on website.

Figure 4: The colour palette of the communication profile

When the final logo was decided, the presentation and communication design templates were disseminated to the consortium. Six (6) templates make up the package of templates:

1. Powerpoint template 4:3
2. Powerpoint template 16:9
3. Table and Charts template
4. Deliverable template Confidential
5. Deliverable template Public
6. Meeting Minutes template

A picture was included for multiple purposes (templates, website, poster, etc.) and a simple design for presentation templates was produced.

Figure 5: The front of the presentation template.

11.2 Carried out

11.2.1 Project website and online presence

The SENSEI website www.senseih2020.eu will serve as main news and information hub for all dissemination and communication activities throughout the project period. The website is a key tool to increase project awareness and to target stakeholders effectively.

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Visitors will find information about the project and partners, recent news, Newsletters, deliverables and upcoming events. Social media feeds are integrated on the website, thus being an effective way of keeping the website up to date.

WordPress was selected as Content Management System (CMS) for the website. This is an open source, license free CMS with flexible templates, various editorial functionalities and marginal maintenance costs. Additionally, Wordpress was selected because it is easy to integrate with the stakeholder support platform EngageSuite.

Figure 6: The structure of the website.

Initially, the structure of the website was decided. Secondly, all web technical features are incorporated such as Google Analytics for web analysis purposes, MailChimp to serve as Newsletter generator, SENSEI email verifications for contact forms, website validations for Google index, social media integrations and verifications at the website, multi-language plug-in, GDPR compliance and Search Engine Optimizations. The SENSEI website is optimized for the Google Chrome browser.

PAY-FOR-PERFORMANCE to drive energy efficiency in Europe
Smart Energy Services to Maximize the Energy Efficiency in the European Building Stock

Pay-for-performance in a nutshell
Pay-for-performance (PFP) is a way to achieve significant, longer-scale energy savings in the European building stock and attract additional investment and new business models.

Pay-for-performance as a game changer
PFP can have a dramatic impact by increasing the number of energy efficiency programs.

PFP can significantly reduce the greenhouse gas emissions from the European building stock.
SENSEI will develop business models based on PFP and provide an incentive for market players to increase investments in more energy efficient buildings, for example, by the refurbishment of buildings and implementation of whole-building retrofits. The need to further ramp-up energy efficiency in the European building stock to avoid CO₂ emissions from energy generation, along with an interest in better use of digital energy market data and analytics to encourage efficiency gains.

PFP can have a substantial positive effect on buildings in Europe by attracting capital to improve existing and energy efficiency.
SENSEI will act as the energy consumption customer at the centre of new transaction models. Transaction models based on PFP give greater transparency in the energy performance of buildings and pay rates. Most of all, PFP benefits the end-user by reducing their energy bills. Additionally, improved buildings result in a higher standard of living for residents and a higher value for building owners.

PFP can have a dramatic impact on the energy system by reducing costs and capturing energy efficiency as a grid resource.
SENSEI will deliver a transaction model based on PFP for stakeholders to create and replicate. When PFP spreads in the market, it will also have a positive side effect on the energy grid by reducing energy efficiency as a grid resource. Outside the European Union, the first generation of PFP has shown that energy efficiency programs can help stabilize the grid and retail rates. When customers save energy during the grid's critical times, energy efficiency can serve as a system capacity resource and/or distribution system infrastructure upgrade. Secondly, PFP can reduce costs in the energy system by providing flexibility and capacity reductions. Instead of system operators to invest in a new energy plant, PFP programs can to a certain extent protect investments in new and existing.

Twitter feed snippet:
SENSEI H2020
The new H2020 project SENSEI aims at...
Read more about SENSEI project: [#SENSEIproject](#)

Figure 7: The frontpage of the SENSEI website

The social media Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube are integrated into the website. Feeds from Twitter is present at the front page. All social media channels are initiated for dissemination of deliverables, press releases, partners attending events and stakeholder outreach.

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Figure 8: SENSEI Posts on Twitter and LinkedIn

11.2.2 Project flyer, infographics and poster

The initial steps in developing the SENSEI flyers, infographics and poster are taken. SENSEI has a version one of a flyer, a version one of infographics and when the elements to go into a poster are ready, a version one of a poster can be made. SENSEI will throughout the project lifetime develop the communication packages and make adjustments in hand-outs and presentations according to preliminary results and final results in the project. SENSEI can present:

1. A version one of a flyer focusing on the importance of SENSEI towards the European market in Energy Efficiency.
2. A version one of amendments to the flyer, such as two examples of P4P and stakeholder benefits (second version will be like flyer's layout)
3. A version one of infographics "CASH-FLOW" presenting an example of a P4P business case and the interplay of parties.
4. A sketch of a poster that needs to be aligned according to the communication profile.

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Figure 9: SENSEI flyer for printing hand-outs (A4 upright folded in the middle)

Figure 10: Amendments to flyer focusing on stakeholder benefits and two examples from USA.

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Figure 11: Infographics to go into presentations and posters. Infographic is on website as well.

Smart Energy Services to Improve the Energy Efficiency of the European Building Stock
EC HORIZON 2020 project: 847066

The importance of SENSEI

- Puts energy consumers at the centre of the power system:
 - Energy efficiency is valuable for consumers on its own. If we provide a way to increase the value of an energy efficiency intervention, we directly provide more value to consumers
 - Provides a mechanism to steer energy efficiency interventions towards measures that are beneficial for both the building owners and the power system
- Makes energy efficiency more attractive for private investments:
 - Energy efficiency improvement is a financing challenge rather than a technical challenge. Public funding is not enough; we need to mobilize private capital as well
 - SENSEI will identify the conditions (risk sharing agreements, guarantees, ...) under which the proposed transaction model can improve the risk/return rating of an energy retrofit project

The main ambition behind SENSEI

- To provide a transaction model, based on P4P scheme, that will allow energy efficiency to be regarded as an exploitable resource for the power system.
- To plan for pilots in the EU where:
 - > stakeholders that are willing to compensate energy efficiency and
 - > stakeholders that can bring potential projects (building owners and ESCOs)
 - > get together to implement the SENSEI model

The interplay between P4P schemes and EPC projects

Pert diagram of the project

The P4P concept as the vehicle to distribute the value of energy savings

The SRI as a bridge between P4P and demand response incentives

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Figure 12: An initial version of a SENSEI poster.

11.2.3 Identification of key messages and selling points

The GA has preliminary outlined key messages (table 2.2) and stakeholders. Key messages that will be conveyed to stakeholders. The purpose of the key messages is to target the communication according to stakeholders and the purpose of selling points is to talk the “business language” targeted the different stakeholders. Identification of key messages and selling points will be a part of the DCP (D3.1) delivered M6. At this stage some preliminary key messages and selling points can be presented.

Stakeholders groups	Benefits	Key messages	Essence	Selling points
Building owners	Building owners will increase the benefits they get from an energy retrofit project, as well as turn them into an investable asset to attract private financing and minimize upfront capital costs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Credible investment opportunities - Attracting capital in energy efficiency - Refurbishment of buildings - New revenue stream - Increased building value - Frees up capital - Installation of smart metering - M&V support in the different transactions between the parties 	A new revenue stream	Improvements of building, installations and maintenance. Building Owners can benefit by getting more private investors involved in retrofit of buildings with the aim of energy efficiency. Besides reducing CO2 (productive buildings), building owners can get happier tenants (comfortable buildings). Building owners get buildings of higher value.
EE Project developers, ESCOs, aggregators, EPC facilitators	ESCOs will expand their market reach by collaborating with “energy efficiency aggregators” that create and broker portfolios of energy retrofit projects.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New business opportunities and business modelling. - Intermediaries will get more instruments for business. - Business models developed will benefit players and the value chain in the energy market. 	New business models	Cash-flow can be delivered through an Energy Performance Contracting (EPC) with the utility and does not rely on repayment by the building owner or the tenants. An agreement can be long-term and generate many more years of cash flow, and hence, can both finance and maintain much deeper efficiency installations.
Power system operators	System operators will be supported in rolling out incentive schemes that aim at steering energy efficiency interventions towards measures that are beneficial for both the building owners and the grid and will	Smart design of incentives for energy efficiency (permanently reducing energy consumption) can also lead to increase capacity for buildings to provide flexibility services to the grid.	Bringing the cost down	When end-users save energy during the grid’s critical times, energy efficiency can serve as a system capacity resource and/or defer distribution system infrastructure upgrades. Secondly, P4P can reduce costs in the energy system by providing flexibility and capacity reduction. Instead of investing in

	become part of the value chain of energy efficiency improvements.			a new energy plant, P4P programs can to a certain extent prolong investments in wires and cables.
Utilities, Energy providers	Utilities will diversify their revenue streams by providing new energy efficiency services (along with energy supply services) and benefiting from the value that energy efficiency brings to the power grid.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New load management resource - Location-specific and reliable - Only pay for units received - Rate-based: Earnings opportunity - No gross revenue loss - No unit sale loss 	Avoid the death spiral	<p>The power system will benefit from an increased value of an energy efficiency intervention. Energy Providers will be able to provide building owners incentives for load reduction.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pays only for the actual metered energy savings. - P4P creates a standard – and powerful – encouragement to the developer and investor to make sure the efficiency is delivered and stays persistent. - Efficiency becomes locally provable and so locally targetable.
Investors	Investors will have new opportunities to invest in energy efficiency: P4P-ready energy retrofit projects will be particularly attractive for investors due to increased and stable returns on investment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Long term reliable cash-flow from a stable, asset-based investment - Finance based on utility agreement - Stronger counterparties - Lower and rated payment risk - Well-understood instruments - Greater liquidity through utility-level portfolio aggregation. 	Long term contracting with utility	Better trade-off and return-of-investment. Besides green investment opportunities, Financial Institutions will benefit from more transparent Return of Investment (ROI) and profit from energy savings. Investors can get a fair deal of the revenues as a result of retrofit and energy efficiency.
Policy makers	P4P offers a solution to the logjam currently facing the market for energy efficiency. By metering energy savings over time, P4P rewards improvements that persist over decades, while also lowering the cost of evaluation, measurement and verification.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Domestic jobs - Environmental and climate benefit (CO2) - Instrument to balance the grid (flexibility in distributed energy) - Cost reduction (energy system) - Enhanced building stock - Price stability - No incentives required - Higher living standard and healthier buildings (population health) 	Scalable and flexible deep energy efficiency	Getting what you are paying for. In P4P programs, the players pay only for actual performance. Thus even if incentive Euro were added on top of a EE project, regulators could know that none of those Euros would be spent unless the contracted-for benefit actually showed up.

Table 1: Preliminary description of key messages and selling points.

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11.2.4 Press release and initial invitation to stakeholders

After the KoM a press release was produced to present the project and overall scope of the project. A brief description of the project was released, and a targeted press release was prepared to be sent it out in due time as part of the engagement invitations to stakeholders.

Figure 13: Brief description of the project.

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INVITATION to stakeholders to join

Take part in the development of a new innovative financing model to increase energy efficiency and maximize financial returns

15 November 2019

New financing models are needed to mobilize more private capital to increase the energy efficiency of the European building stock. The EC funded HORIZON 2020 project SENSEI is developing a smart energy service that can help accelerate the uptake of energy efficiency refurbishments in Europe, and provide value for the grid, and for investors. Making buildings more energy efficient is critical to meet climate goals, avoid the construction of new power plants, reduce grid infrastructure costs, and save customers money on energy bills.

Today most energy efficiency initiatives in the European building stock are funded by building owner collaborations and public subsidies. This is not enough to reach higher energy efficiency targets. New financing models can provide stronger incentives for investors to bring in more private capital into the market to increase the number of retrofit projects. SENSEI, inspired by USA-led experience in the field, will adapt the Pay-for-Performance (P4P) model (more on P4P in the box) for the European energy market.

Financing institutions and private investors face complexity and financial risk in the green transition in transition of buildings into greener buildings. P4P is a concept that can bring clarification of tradeoffs and more transparency in "What do you get for your investment?", both in terms of risk and benefit. Players with different interest in energy will get stronger incentives in energy transition, because they can share risks and benefits in financial investments. Energy efficiency will potentially give multiple benefits to players in the market, like higher property value to building owners, comfort to the end-user, new business opportunities to aggregators and more.

HORIZON 2020 project SENSEI funded by the European Commission started 1 September 2019 and had the first partner meeting in Brussels, 17-18 September 2019 (The project consists of 13 partners from 8 countries).

www.senseih2020.eu | @senseih2020 | #senseih2020 | [Twitter](#) | [LinkedIn](#)

For enrolment and more information:

Contact IECEP (Institute for European Energy and Climate Policy, The Netherlands) for more information on SENSEI project: Filippos Anagnostopoulos, filippos@ieeco.org

For more information:

Contact CIMNE (Centre Internacional de Metodes Numerics en Energinyaria, SPAIN) for more information in the technical/data field: Dr. Stoyan Danov, sdanov@cimne.upc.edu

Contact HEBES (Hebes Intelligence Single Member I.K.E., GREECE) for more information on the background: Dr. Sotiris Papadelis, spapadelis@hebes.it

Pay-for-Performance: Rewarding savings instead of measures

Pay-for-Performance (P4P) links payments to proven savings. P4P schemes make use of an innovative concept to deliver energy savings through a flexible approach allowing innovation, reduction of costs and increasing customer value.

Most current energy efficiency programs work through rebates and incentives paid upfront for specific technical measures and estimated energy savings. In P4P schemes, those who deliver energy efficiency are only paid after the efficiency improvements have been implemented and on the basis of proven and measured savings.

P4Ps are emerging in the US as an innovative way to increase energy savings by engaging energy providers, attracting investors and motivating consumers to cut energy consumption. With increased confidence in its performance, energy efficiency can be rewarded as an energy system resource.

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Figure 14: Press release will be sent bilaterally with invitations with a targeted approach to stakeholders.

11.2.5 Partners online presentation of the project and e-news

The project objectives and potential impacts were shortly after KoM uploaded as e-news on partners websites. The purpose was to communicate to business relations who regularly visit partner websites. Below is a list of partners who has uploaded e-news of SENSEI on their corporate website. More partners will be added as the DCP is published.

Partner	Link to e-news on company website	Link to Newsletter(s)/other online magazines
IEECP	http://www.ieecp.org/project/sensei/	http://www.ieecp.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/IEECP-newsletter-5.pdf
GECO	https://www.geco-global.com/sensei/	
UNICAL	https://www.unical.it/portale/portaltemplates/view/view.cfm?93199	https://www.approdonews.it/giornale/efficienza-energetica-unical-nel-progetto-europeo-sensei/ https://www.lameziainstrada.com/cultura-e-societa/efficienza-energetica-anche-lunical-nel-progettoeuropeo-sensei http://www.lametino.it/Ultimora/efficienza-energetica-anche-l-unical-nel-progetto-europeo.html

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		https://www.noidicalabria.it/investimenti-in-efficienza-energetica-passano-dalluniversita-dellacalabria/ https://www.calabrianews24.com/rende-l-efficienza-energetica-passa-dall-unical-con-il-progettosensei/ http://www.meteoweb.eu/2019/09/efficienza-energetica-anche-lunical-nel-progetto-europeosensei/1318234/ http://ildispaccio.it/cosenza/223876-efficienza-energetica-anche-l-unical-nel-progetto-europeo-sensei https://www.calabriadirettanews.com/2019/09/24/efficienza-energetica-anche-lunical-nel-progettoeuropeo-sensei/
CIMNE	https://www.cimne.com/webcimne/sigpro/Ficha.aspx?id=838 https://www.beegroup-cimne.com/portfolio/sensei-smart-energy-services-integrating-the-multiple-benefits-from-improving-the-energy-efficiency-of-the-european-building-stock/	
OMNIA ENERGIA	https://www.omniaenergia.it/progetto-sensei-ai-nastri-di-partenza-con-omnia-energia-protagonista/	

Table 2: List of partners who has uploaded e-news on corporate website.

11.2.6 Presentation of the project at events

Project SENSEI was presented twice at two different events in Italy. The two events were:

1. S3 Forum – Ravenna, Emilia-Romagna, Italy, 17 October 2019
2. KEY ENERGY – The Renewable Energy Expo, Fiera di Rimini, Italy, 5-8 November 2019

Presentations were disseminated at social media and copies of the flyer were disseminated to participants during the events. All events and dissemination activities in the project are tracked and monitored.

FORUM S3

**I CLUSTER E LO SVILUPPO SOSTENIBILE:
RICERCA E INNOVAZIONE PER LE SFIDE DI AGENDA 2030**

I Forum S3 sono momenti di confronto aperti a tutti i soggetti del sistema regionale di innovazione, nati con l'obiettivo di suggerire in maniera continuativa politiche e strumenti di intervento per una più efficace attuazione della Strategia di Specializzazione Intelligente (SSI).

Nel 2019 si è deciso di orientare i Forum S3 verso indicazioni di policy per la ricerca e l'innovazione, focalizzate sul tema dell'Agenda 2030 per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile

3 ottobre 2019 | Modena
Residenza San Filippo Neri, Via Sant'Orsola 52

8 ottobre 2019 | Bologna
FICO Eataty World, Via Paolo Canali 8

17 ottobre 2019 | Ravenna
Palazzo Rasponi dalle Teste, Piazza John Fitzgerald Kennedy 12

Registrazione

Modena, 3 Ottobre 2019

- CITTÀ DEL FUTURO - Nuove prospettive per un ambiente urbano sostenibile | Sessione Plenaria 9.00 - 10.30
- Parallela - Ospedali 4.0 e sostenibile 10.30 - 13.00
- Parallela - Rigenerazione e riattivazione urbana 10.30 - 13.00
- Parallela - Mobilità e sistemi di popolazione sostenibili 10.30 - 13.00

Bologna, 8 Ottobre 2019

- UOMO, LA TERRA, IL CLIMA - Sistemi agricoli sostenibili | Sessione Plenaria 9.00 - 10.30
- Parallela - Alimentazione e salute 10.30 - 13.00
- Parallela - Recupero di sottoprodotti 10.30 - 13.00
- Parallela - I dati al servizio della terra e del clima 10.30 - 13.00

Ravenna, 17 Ottobre 2019

- RISORSE DI OGNI VALORE PER IL DOMANI - Sistemi produttivi efficienti e innovativi | Sessione Plenaria 9.00 - 10.30
- Parallela - Nuove soluzioni per il packaging 10.30 - 13.00
- Parallela - Materiali innovativi ed ecosostenibili 10.30 - 13.00
- Parallela - Efficienza energetica ed energie rinnovabili 10.30 - 13.00

[Dettagli personali](#)

KEY ENERGY

THE RENEWABLE ENERGY EXPO

5 - 8 NOVEMBRE 2019 FIERA DI RIMINI - ITALIA

organizzato da **ITALIAN EXHIBITION GROUP** Building the future | in contemporanea con **ECOMONDO** | keyenergy.it

Figure 15: SENSEI was presented at two (2) events in Italy.

11.3 Scheduled

11.3.1 Initial description and first version of presentation video

Two (2) videos will be produced in the project lifetime. Video No. 1 is a presentation video that explains the essence of the project.

[>> Link to first version of a SENSEI presentation video](#)

Figure 16: First version of the SENSEI presentation video

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The purpose is to deliver visuals that in approximately one minute can catch the eye and the interest to visit SENSEI website to read more. Below is the initial storyboard for video No. 1 that will be produced by M4.

Time	Theme	Script	Graphics
00.00	<i>What is the challenge</i>	Buildings alone account for approximately 40% of energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions in the EU. So, improving their energy efficiency is essential in the fight against climate change. But financing these improvements is often difficult. If we make energy improvements for buildings something investable, their decarbonization become far more accessible. This is the idea behind the SENSEI project	Rapid succession of buildings' smoking chimneys, Single family houses, Multi family houses, Apartment blocks, Offices, Skyscrapers
	<i>What is SENSEI's contribution?</i>	SENSEI will provide mechanisms to steer energy efficiency interventions towards measures that are beneficial for both the building owners and the power system. By doing so, we can design energy efficiency projects that are especially attractive for investors. This will improve the buildings we live and work in, and significantly reduce our carbon footprint.	SENSEI Logo Oversimplified , icon-based image of the power system Or, simplified sensei model graphic.
	<i>Who can benefit from SENSEI?</i>	Building owners get better and more comfortable buildings, improved indoor climate, and a lower environmental footprint Investors get green investment opportunities, and returns that are based on verified savings Energy system operators get cost effective options to ensure the stability and adequacy of the energy system, while pursuing its decarbonization The environment also wins from decreases energy demand, and reduced emissions of greenhouse gases	An icon for each category
	<i>Where can you learn more SENSEI?</i>	Learn more about SENSEI on our website [1 second break] and on our social media.	www.senseih2020.eu Twitter, LinkedIn,

	<i>Outro</i>		<p>SENSEI and EU-logo</p> <p>Text: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under the Grant Agreement No. 847066</p>
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Table 3: Initial storyboard for video No. 1 – a presentation video.

11.3.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan

According to the project timeline, a DCP is D3.1 and will be delivered in month six (6). The DCP will contain a communication strategy and an action plan for all further communication activities in project SENSEI including dissemination deeds. The DCP will bring a detailed action plan and be an overview of:

1. Key communication messages to stakeholders
2. Plan for website development and forward online activity
3. Production of use-cases
4. Production of info-graphics
5. Posters for presentation at conferences, events etc.
6. Four (4) articles on different related topics (translated)
7. Four (4) press releases on different related topics (translated)
8. Production of two (2) presentation videos
9. Production of two (2) policy briefs targeted stakeholders
10. Production of a presentation for partners to use at conferences, events, etc.
11. Plan for partners to participate in dissemination events
12. Production of six (6) articles for project Newsletter
13. Plan for identification and activate network of journalists in the areas like green energy, renewables, construction and building, consumers, green investments, green innovation (technology, energy efficiency, etc.)
14. Plan for contacting media and press contact in Netherlands, Italy, Greece, Spain, Belgium, Denmark and Germany.
15. Production of three (3) webinars on different relevant topics
16. Production of one (1) policy event
17. Production of two (2) stakeholder workshops
18. Production of two (2) capacity building events
19. Production of content for stakeholder engagement (EngageSuite)
20. Production of KPI's and tracking of activities
21. Plan for collaborative events for bringing knowledge between EU projects
22. Plan for production of scientific publications

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11.3.3 Collaboration with other EU projects

The first steps have been taken to bridge knowledge between SENSEI and other relevant EU project. The purpose is to ensure a collaboration for synergy creation. For SENSEI it is important to benefit from other project's findings and to create collaboration in e.g. workshops or other events of matter over the whole duration of the project. In order to avoid duplication of work, build on already produced sound analysis and exploit synergies, SENSEI has identified a list of projects also funded by the EC. Below is a list showing the progressions in bridging.

NOVICE – New Buildings Energy Renovation Business Models incorporating dual energy service	SENSEI has contacted NOVICE and established collaboration. NOVICE participated in the first SENSEI introductory webinar about “What is P4P?”
TripleA - Enhancing at an Early Stage the Investment Value Chain of Energy Efficiency Projects	SENSEI has reached out to TripleA in order to organize a first webinar and arrange a EUSEW event together
LAUNCH - Sustainable Energy Assets through standardised, investor grade Energy Performance Contracts, standardised risk assessment protocols for investors	SENSEI has reached out to LAUNCH in order to organize a first webinar and arrange a EUSEW event together
PROSPECT – Peer Powered Cities and Regions	SENSEI will contact soon
EDI-NET – The Energy Data Innovation Network; using smart meter data, campaigns and networking to increase the capacity of public authorities to implement sustainable energy policy	SENSEI will contact soon
SHERPA – Shared knowledge for Energy Renovation in buildings by Public Administrations	SENSEI will contact soon
CESBA MED – Sustainable MED Cities, INTERREG MED Programme	SENSEI will contact soon
Sim4Blocks – Simulation Supported Real Time Energy Management in Building Blocks	SENSEI will contact soon
GuarantEE – Energy Efficiency with Performance Guarantees in Private and Public Sector	SENSEI will contact soon
FALCO – Financing Ambitious Local Climate Objectives	SENSEI will contact soon
InterConnect - A step in effective energy management	SENSEI will contact soon
AMBIENCE - Actively Managed Buildings with Energy Performance Contracting	SENSEI will contact soon
ENTROPY - Design and deploy an innovative IT ecosystem targeting at improving energy efficiency through consumers understanding, engagement and behavioural changes	SENSEI will contact soon

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Dr Bob - Demand Response energy management solution optimises the local energy production, consumption and storage in real time	SENSEI will contact soon
TABEDE - Towards Building ready for Demand response	SENSEI will contact soon
RESPOND - Integrated demand Response Solution towards energy Positive Neighbourhoods	SENSEI will contact soon

Table 4: List of other EC funded Horizon 2020 projects that SENSEI will reach out to.

11.3.4 Scientific publications and dissemination of knowledge

Scientific publications/papers made during the project will be disseminated according to the GA. No scientific publications have yet been produced in the project but the means for dissemination of knowledge have been done been established e.g. Open Access, stakeholder engagement platform EngageSuite and social media channels.

12 Lessons learned and adjustments

The WPL in communication and dissemination has decided to establish an Editorial Board. The Editorial Board will be organized as a horizontal function supporting Cluster 3 and consist of partner's experts in energy efficiency. The Editorial Board is not a duplication of the Cluster 3. This action has been taken acknowledging the fact that communication and dissemination activities in project SENSEI need be organized better. See appendix 1: Editorial Board Guidelines.

By organizing an Editorial Board as a supporting function, defining the task of the board and describing the procedures within the organization, the goal is to increase the content flow and communication efficiency. Suggesting the Editorial Board is trying to find a solution to solve a problem of a "bottleneck" in communication tasks and to raise quality in the material's content.

The purpose of an Editorial Board is to bring the partner's experts in energy efficiency closer to the table for communication reasons. During the first months of the project the WPL in communication and dissemination has realized a great diversity of opinions internally on what P4P is, mostly because P4P in reality comes in such a great diversity of variations.

The communication that has to convey the important messages to potential stakeholders must be clear and concise, and the Editorial Board will support to mitigate that diverse opinions overtake and influence the communication and in worst case impact the results of the project negatively. In addition, the WPL in communication and dissemination can foresee that an Editorial Board can be beneficial later in the project to establish small agile communication teams e.g. story boarding, video production and composition of supporting guidelines.

The Editorial Board is attributed to the fact that almost all partners have PMs in WP2 and 3 (10 out of 13 have PM). Establishing an editorial board in an EU project is new to the WPL, and it is a need the WPL did not see in forehand.

Instead of non-experts in energy efficiency like GECO trying to guess what is the right message, then turn it around by getting the content right from the beginning and then communicate it. Establishing the editorial board is an attempt to prevent the non-experts to reinvent the wheel every time, communication people have to communicate – trying to optimize the flow of content by broaden the group of experts.

13 Conclusion

Deliverable D3.3 has its first due date month four (4) and wraps up what has been achieved during that time. Communication and dissemination started on day one of the SENSEI project in order to make the required preparations prior to KoM. Expectations in the project communication and dissemination were aligned among all partners during the KoM e.g. by establishing a cluster of partners named Cluster 3 Dissemination, Communication and Outreach.

In addition, the WPL in communication and dissemination has taken the first steps to establish an Editorial Board as a supporting function to Cluster 3.

The next D3.3 milestone will be month 22. The SENSEI project is a very important project in designing and testing P4P business models in Europe and has taken actions towards of raising the communication bar.

14 Appendix

Editorial Board Guidelines

Establishing Editorial Board

Cluster 3 (Communication, dissemination and outreach) had a coordination telco Monday 4 November 2019 and decided to establish an editorial board involving all partners.

The purpose is to optimize the flow of content and messaging that needs to be communicated. The task of the Editorial Board is to support Cluster 3.

It is crucial for the project to get experts in the editorial board in order to frame the communication content and prioritize the wording to ensure engagement of important stakeholders. We have to ensure that we put as big an effort into Cluster 3 as much as possible.

To ensure flexibility Cluster 3 suggests a structure and procedure outlined like this:

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Structure

- The editorial board will be organized as a horizontal function and refer to Cluster 3. The editorial board will be a supporting function to Cluster 3.
- Most of the communication will be by email. The editorial board will have ad-hoc online meetings.
- When the editorial board is established, the editorial board will be included in the communication and dissemination plan.
- The editorial board will have to support all communication and dissemination activities in the project lifetime on request from Cluster 3 leader or a Cluster 3 member.

Procedure

- Each partner points out an expert to be a part of the editorial board.
- To get a good mix of knowledge/expertise in the editorial board, each representative writes a few lines about themselves in the field of expertise (Fill in the table below).
- Having this list of experts, Cluster 3 leader can ask for assistance and ask an expert to give feedback.
- In respect to partners internal planning and work streams, Cluster 3 leader can give short deadlines to mitigate “bottle necks”.
- Experts in the editorial board can at an editorial telco suggest new activities and/or send an email to all in the board.
- Before uploaded to website or send out, Cluster 3 will have to approve the content.
- Cluster 3 leader will upload to website or ask members to send out e.g. if it is at national level.
- In cases of content targeted national bodies in own language it can be send out by partners.

Cluster 3 leader: Carsten Gydahl, GECO Global

Cluster 3 members: Carsten Gydahl GECO, Filippos Anagnostopoulos IEECP, Alessandro Celestino RAP, Marta Calvo Cortina GENCAT, Sotiris Papadelis HEBES, Giovanni Pede SINERGIE, Geert Goorden FACTOR4, Nicklas Badum DBT.

Editorial board: TBD

Q&A's:

- What is the difference between introducing “Cluster 3” and an editorial board?
Answer: Not all partners are represented in Cluster 3 and some persons in Cluster 3 are communication experts and maybe not experts in areas like energy efficiency, P4P, etc.
- Why not have the communication persons (who are in the global contact list in Dropbox) in the editorial board? Answer: The editorial board will consist of experts. Cluster 3 will approve communication material before publication.
- Can a partner have the same person sitting in the editorial board and Cluster 3?
Answer: Yes

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